

SYNTHETICAL EXPERIMENTS IN THE PYRONE SERIES. ATTEMPTED OXIDATION OF CHROMANONES WITH SELENIUM DIOXIDE. PART I.

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The chromanones are not oxidised with selenium dioxide to the chromones, though the flavanones and chalcones are oxidised with selenium dioxide to the flavones.

The observation of Venkataraman and co-workers (Mahal, Rai and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 866; Mahal and Venkataraman, *ibid.*, 1936, 569) that certain flavanones or even some chalcones are oxidised to flavones by selenium dioxide led the authors to attempt the oxidation of chromanones with selenium dioxide for the unambiguous synthesis of substituted chromones which cannot be synthesised by the methods known at present.

The chromanones have been obtained by the cyclisation of the phenoxypropionic acids using phosphorus pentoxide in benzene solution. The phenoxypropionic acids have been prepared by following the method of Perkin, Rây and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 941; Perkin, Pollard and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1937, 49) by reacting *o*- and *p*-chlorophenol, *o*- and *p*-nitrophenol, *o*- and *p*-cresols, α - and β -naphthol with β -chloropropionic acid in alkaline medium. It should be noted that when attempts are made for cyclisation by 85% sulphuric acid, the yields are very poor and in some cases the phenols are sulphonated. The chromanones have been characterised by condensing them with veratraldehyde in presence of dry hydrochloric acid in acetic acid solution forming 3-veratrylidene derivatives. The α -naphthachromanone, prepared by this method, has been found to be identical with the compound obtained by Pfeiffer and Grimmer (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 911) from 2-acetyl-1-naphthol.

The oxidation of the chromanones is, however, attended with difficulties. In view of the observation of Chakravarti and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407, 619; 1932, 9, 25, 31, 389; 1936, 31, 619, 649) that the halogen atom and the nitro group favour γ -pyrone formation in Simonis' reaction, it was thought that the halogenated

chromanones. *e.g.*, 6-chlorochromanone, would give the corresponding chromone more easily. 6-Chlorochromanone has been oxidised with selenium dioxide, but with negative results. All attempts to synthesise the chromones by the oxidation of the chromanones with selenium dioxide under varying conditions of temperature and in different solvents, *e.g.*, xylene, rectified spirit, amyl alcohol, have been unsuccessful. In all cases metallic selenium is precipitated and when the product is treated with dilute alkali a coloured solution is obtained, which on acidification gives an amorphous yellow substance; but the latter does not freely dissolve in alkali and resists all attempts at crystallisation. The identity of these yellow substances could not be established but qualitative tests prove the presence of a high percentage of selenium in these substances. When the reactions are done in amyl alcoholic solution crystalline substances containing selenium separate. The presence of an *ortho*-diketone, one of the possible products of oxidation, could not be detected.

It was thought that the halogen atom instead of exerting a favourable influence might conceivably interfere, and hence nitrochromanones have been oxidised but with no better results. In order to eliminate the unfavourable influence of the halogen atom or the nitro group, if any, the methylchromanones have been oxidised but with the same result.

These unsuccessful attempts for the oxidation of the different chromanones led the authors to doubt the general applicability of Venkataraman's method for the oxidation of flavanones and chalcones, and hence chalcones containing halogen atom and nitro group in the benzene nucleus have been prepared and oxidised with selenium dioxide; but in conformity with Venkataraman's observations the oxidation is effected very smoothly with the formation of flavones in highly satisfactory yield. The chalcones are evidently transformed into flavanones which undergo oxidation. Thus the following chalcones (I) have been oxidised to the corresponding flavones (II): 3':4'-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-chlorochalkone (I, R=Cl; R₁=H); 3':4'-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-3-chlorochalkone (I, R=H; R₁=Cl); 3':4'-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-3-nitro-6-methylchalkone (I, R=Me; R₁=NO₂).

(II)

In view of the fact that the chromanones are not oxidised, while the chalcones, irrespective of any substituent in the benzene nucleus, undergo smooth oxidation with selenium dioxide without the formation of selenium complexes, it is evident that the phenyl group in the pyrone nucleus is responsible for this smooth oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method for the Preparation of the Phenoxypropionic Acids.—The phenol (1 mol.) was dissolved in caustic potash solution (30 %) and heated on the water-bath. The amount of the caustic potash used was about twice the amount required to neutralise the phenol. The solution of the neutralised β -chloropropionic acid (1 mol.) was then added in small quantities at a time to the heated solution during 1 hour and the reaction mixture further heated for 2-4 hours. The cold solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and the latter acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was collected, again dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and the precipitate obtained on acidification was crystallised from a solvent.

General Method for the Preparation of the Chromanones.—The phenoxypropionic acid (1 part) was dissolved in benzene (20 parts) and the solution refluxed with phosphorus pentoxide (3 parts) for 10 hours. The supernatant benzene layer was then decanted off and the pasty residue was decomposed with powdered ice and extracted with hot benzene. The benzene extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and dried and on removal of benzene the residue was either crystallised from a suitable solvent or distilled in *vacuo*. The phenoxypropionic acids and the chromanones prepared are described in Table I.

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-5-chlorochalkone.—A solution of 2-oxy-5-chloroacetophenone (4 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) was treated with caustic potash (50%, 15 c.c.) and the red solution was refluxed on the water-bath for 1 hour. The solution was cooled, acidified and the precipitate crystallised from glacial acetic acid as reddish orange needles, m.p. 174°, yield 3 g. It gives a brown colour with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 11.35. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 11.15 per cent).

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-6-chloroflavone was obtained by the oxidation of the above compound (2 g.) in amyl alcohol (30 c.c.) by selenium dioxide (2 g.) by refluxing at 150-60° for 12 hours. The solution was filtered hot from the precipitated metallic selenium when on cooling crystals appeared. It was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 194°, yield 1.5 g. It gives no colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 11.40. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 11.21 per cent).

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-3-chlorochalkone was obtained from 2-hydroxy-3-chloroacetophenone (4 g.) and veratraldehyde (4 g.) as in the previous case. It crystallised from alcohol as orange plates, m.p. 163-64°, yield 4 g. (Found : Cl, 11.45. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 11.15 per cent).

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-8-chloroflavone was obtained from 3' : 4'-dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-3-chlorochalkone (2 g.) by oxidation with selenium dioxide (2 g.) in amyl alcohol (20 c.c.). On removal of amyl alcohol from the filtered solution by steam distillation the residue was crystallised from benzene as chocolate needles, m.p. 110° (decomp.), yield 1 g. It gives an ash-coloured precipitate with ferric chloride. (Found : Cl, 11.48. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 11.21 per cent).

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylchalkone, prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone (4 g.) and veratraldehyde (4 g.), crystallised from dilute acetic acid as chocolate needles with a green reflex, m.p. 175°, yield 4 g. It gives a blood-red colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : N, 4.13. $C_{18}H_{17}O_4N$ requires N, 4.08 per cent).

3' : 4'-Dimethoxy-6-methyl-8-nitroflavone was obtained from the above compound (2 g.) by oxidation with selenium dioxide (2 g.) in amyl alcohol (40 c.c.). The hot solution deposited crystals on cooling which were recrystallised from amyl alcohol as brown needles, m.p. 244-45° (decomp.), yield 1 g. (Found : N, 4.23. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.11 per cent).

TABLE I

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from β -chloro-propionic acid and	M. p.	Analysis		Remarks.
				Found.	Calc.	
β -(<i>p</i> -Chloro)-phenoxy-propionic acid (I)	$C_9H_9O_3Cl$	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	138-39°	Cl, 18.05%	17.71	Shining plates from alcohol
6-Chlorochromanone	$C_9H_7O_3Cl$	(I) & P_2O_5	106°	20.0	19.5	Light yellow needles from alcohol
3-Veratrylidene derivative	$C_{10}H_{16}O_4Cl$	—	151-52°	10.96	10.74	Orange plates from alcohol
β -(<i>o</i> -Chloro)-phenoxy-propionic acid (II)	$C_9H_9O_3Cl$	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	108-9°	17.6	17.71	Colourless needles
8-Chlorochromanone	$C_9H_7O_3Cl$	(II) & P_2O_5	65°	19.8	19.5	Light yellow needles
3-Veratrylidene derivative	$C_{10}H_{16}O_4Cl$	—	110-11°	10.85	10.74	Yellow needles
β -(<i>p</i> -Nitro)-phenoxypropionic acid (III)	$C_9H_9O_3N$	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	118-19°	N, 6.98	6.64	Grey needles
6-Nitrochromanone	$C_9H_7O_3N$	(III) & P_2O_5	176-77°	N, 7.23	7.25	Dirty white needles
3-Veratrylidene derivative	$C_{10}H_{15}O_4N$	—	190-91°	N, 4.18	4.11	Yellow needles
β -(<i>o</i> -Nitro)-phenoxypropionic acid (IV)	$C_9H_9O_3N$	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	121-22°	N, 7.0	6.64	Grey needles from water
8-Nitrochromanone	$C_9H_7O_3N$	(IV) & P_2O_5	126-27°	N, 7.28	7.25	Light yellow needles
3-Veratrylidene derivative	$C_{10}H_{15}O_4N$	—	179-80°	N, 4.43	4.11	Yellow needles from acetic acid
* β -(2-) Naphthoxypropionic acid (V)	$C_{13}H_{12}O_3$	β -Naphthol	144-45°	C, 72.40 H, 5.89	72.22 5.55	Colourless needles
β -Naphthachromanone	$C_{13}H_{10}O_4$	(V) & P_2O_5	b p. 185-87/9mm.	C, 78.91 H, 5.64	78.79 5.56	Yellow oil
*Semicarbazone	$C_{14}H_{13}O_4N_3$	—	m. p. 227° (decomp.)	N, 16.62	16.47	Light yellow plates from alcohol

TABLE I (contd.).

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from β -chloro-propionic acid and α -Naphthol	M.p.	Analysis Found :	Remarks.
* β -(1-Naphthoxy)propionic acid (VI)	$C_{13}H_{13}O_3$	α -Naphthol	147-48*	C, 72.40 H, 5.62	72.22 5.55 Identical with the compound described by Pfeiffer and Grimmer (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
α -Naphthachromanone	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2$	(VI) & P_2O_5	104*	---	Light yellow needles, identical with the compound described by Pfeiffer and Grimmer (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
3-Veratrylidene derivative	$C_{23}H_{18}O_4$	—	165-70	C, 76.21 H, 5.24	76.30 5.20 Greenish yellow needles from acetic acid
* β -(<i>o</i> -Methyl)-phenoxypropionic acid (VII)	$C_{10}H_{12}O_3$	<i>o</i> -Cresol	94.5*	C, 67.14 H, 7.05	66.66 6.66 Greyish needles
8-Methylchromanone	$C_{10}H_{10}O_2$	(VII) and P_2O_5 b.p. 128.30*/9mm.	—	C, 74.14 H, 6.30	74.07 6.17 Light yellow liquid
Semicarbazone	$C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$	—	m.p. 230-31* (decomp.)	N, 19.32	19.18 Yellow needles
β -(<i>p</i> -Methyl)-phenoxypropionic acid (VIII)	—	<i>p</i> -Cresol	146*	—	} Identical with the compounds described by Kroll-pfeiffer and Schultze (<i>Ber.</i> , 1924, <i>51</i> , 206).
6-Methylchromanone	—	(VIII) and P_2O_5 b.p. 118-26*/6mm.	—	—	
3-Veratrylidene derivative of 6-methylchromanone	$C_{19}H_{18}O_4$	—	m.p. 131-32	C, 73.13 H, 5.72	73.08 5.77 Orange plates from alcohol

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